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Recent Trends in Consumer Market and Retail

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Abstract

Today's consumers, especially in the urban areas, have far evolved and expect their shopping experience to be seamless across every channel, whether it's a brick-and mortar store, an e-commerce website, a mobile app, or even a phone call with the customer service. Internet of Thing (IoT) technology is already seen to be reshaping and revolutionising the retail industry, yielding advances and new opportunities in customer service, throughout the supply chain, and in brick-and-mortar stores and other channels — including new venues that show a lot of promise, such as home-based connected platforms. As the retail landscape evolves, and as customers place the greatest value on their time and attention, brands have responded by offering greater conveniences, customized experiences, and deeper levels of personalization. Today's customers expect more from brands than ever before, and it's these demands that continue to push the industry forward with great speed. This paper gives an overview of the current market trends that are shaping the Indian retail industry and highlights the specific areas on which retailers are working on with a view to improving customer experience such as premiumisation, social commerce, automated product delivery and touch less commerce.

Key words: Retail, Customer experience, e-commerce, Personalisation, Premiumisation.

Introduction

Retailing and retailers face a rapidly changing market landscape, due largely to the ways modern customers shop: instore, online, through mobile channels, and even with emerging machine-to-machine commerce (Grewal *et al.*, 2017; Rafaeli *et al.*, 2017; Roggeveen *et al.*, 2015; Roggeveen *et al.* 2016). According to A T Kearney report (2019), the retail sector is vital to India's growth, with an 11 percent contribution each to GDP and employment. The economy's third largest sector, retail is poised to grow at a 12 percent annually over next five years, with modern trade and e-commerce expected to lead the growth. It is also one of the country's largest employers, directly accounting for roughly 11 percent of the working population. Retail is also intricately linked with other labour-intensive sectors, such as agriculture, food and beverage, textiles, construction, real estate, and logistics. Further, it indirectly generates job opportunities in allied sectors including warehousing, logistics, and packaging. The Indian retail sector operates through a host of business models which are rapidly evolving with the changing trends and increased use of internet and technology. Outlined below are some of the major retail models, along with their impact and opportunities they offer for Indian retail (Retail FDI in India, Deloitte, October 2018). The role of current technologies, including social media and retailing analytics, and emerging areas, such as the Internet of things, machine learning, artificial intelligence, blockchain technology, and robotics, all of which are likely to change the retail landscape in the future (Grewal *et al.*, 2018).

Retail models and the opportunities they offer

Mechanism of retail	Impact/Opportunities
Cash and carry/Wholesale trading	In India, the consumer goods/FMCG products retailing is clearly divided between urban and rural markets. While the global businesses will focus on the urban markets, the impact of ease of FDI regulations on the existing businesses, both in urban and rural zones, is to be seen in the future. So far, this segment has had automatic investments to the tune of 100 percent as per the regulations set by the government.
Single brand retail trading (SBRT)	The government has eased the sourcing norms in this segment and allowed single brand retail outlets by international brands. The government has now permitted 100 percent FDI under automatic route of SBRT. This immediately opens up opportunities for consumer durables especially the global technology product companies for starting retail operations of their globally successful products in India. The single brand retail model will now be allowed to operate on the e-commerce front, which was not allowed previously as part of the government regulations. Entities engaged in SBRT would be allowed to set off their incremental sourcing of goods from India for global operations during the initial five years beginning from 1 April of the year of the opening of first store against the mandatory sourcing requirement of 30 percent of purchases from India. Sourcing norms will not be applicable upto three years from the commencement of business, that is opening of the first store for entities undertaking SBRT of products having 'state-of-art' and 'cutting edge' technology and where local sourcing is not possible. A committee under the Chairmanship of Secretary, DIPP, with representatives from NITI Aayog, concerned administrative ministry and independent technical expert(s) will examine proposals which would be eligible for the relaxation of the local sourcing criterion under the SBRT norms.
Multi Brand Retail Trade (MBRT)	These are traditional styled shops or retail chains established across India, historically known as 'Bazaars' or "Mom and Pop" stores as known in most countries. The impact of the government-approved route in retailing by grocery chains or consumer goods retailing is perceived to be strong in various analyses done on this market. The global businesses in this segment tend to operate in the urban landscapes with fairly large investments on infrastructure and emphasis on generating high volumes of business. The competition in this segment is expected to be rising significantly in the urban markets. Nevertheless, there is expected to be enough room for growth in the organized retailing of multi-brand establishments. On the regulation front, this is the most debated area in terms of the investment portion allowed into the country. As per the revised FDI policy, the government has allowed 100 percent FDI under automatic route for selling, including by way of e-commerce, processed food as long as they are produced and/ or manufactured in India. This new development is expected to be seen as a significant challenge for many global retail giants altering their plans and usual operating methods.
E-commerce (Marketplace model)	This segment is allowed to bring investments in the automatic mode to the tune of 100 percent. Some of the world's largest brands are operational in this segment and have had significant success in India. However, it is seen to be facing immense competition from several other domestic companies. The

	developments in this area included mergers and acquisitions in a short span of time. Over the last decade, growth in this space has been in triple digits and continues to grow. There is a tremendous level of innovation that this segment is driving with modern retail concepts and use of technology in almost every part of their retail sale process.
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Source: Retail FDI in India, Deloitte, October 2018

Foreign Direct Investments (FDI)

In January 2018, the Government of India (GoI) relaxed the rules for foreign direct investment (FDI) in single-brand retailing, permitting 100 percent investment under the automatic route (previously 49 percent under the automatic route). Further, companies can meet the 30 percent local-sourcing requirement through incremental sourcing by their global businesses for the initial five years. In 2016, the GoI permitted 100 percent FDI in food retailing (including e-commerce) and food processing for locally made or processed products. It has approved a proposal from a multinational technology company focusing on e-commerce to invest USD500 million in foods retailing over five years (on the condition to keep its marketplace and food-retailing arms separate).

To provide clarity and strengthen the regulatory framework governing FDI in e-commerce marketplace entities in India and to provide a level playing field among online and offline traders, the GoI has further amended the consolidated policy in relation to FDI in e-commerce entities which has become applicable to all e-commerce marketplace entities having FDI with effect from 1 February 2019. There are conditions mentioned in the press note, which inter-alia includes prohibition on equity participation by e-commerce players in the vendor entity, restriction on ownership and control over the inventory of the vendor entity, and restriction on the exclusive sale of products on the e-commerce platform of the marketplace player. These amendments are expected to have a far reaching impact on the business carried on by big e-commerce players in India and are likely to require them to have a relook at their business models. Further, it is understood that the GoI is working on a new draft e-commerce policy which is likely to be released in sometime (Deloitte report, Feb., 2019).

Sectoral caps of investments on select relevant activities

Sector/Activity	% of Equity/FDI Cap	Entry Route/ Approval
Cash and carry wholesale trading/wholesale trading (including sourcing from MSEs)	100%	Automatic
Single brand product retail trading (subject to conditions)	100%	Automatic
Multi-brand product retail trading (subject to conditions)	51%	Government
Duty-free shops	100%	Automatic
E-commerce marketplace (subject to conditions)	100%	Automatic

Source: Retail FDI in India, Deloitte, October 2018

Indian retail industry's growth will be fuelled by strong macro-economic factors and favourable demographics

Favourable macro-economic indicators and rapid growth in consumption have been and are expected to continue driving the growth of the retail sector as a whole.

Source: Consumer LEADS, Deloitte, October 2018

India is Asia’s third largest retail market and the world’s fourth largest after the US, China, and Japan(Deloitte analysis).It is one of the fastest growing major economiesin the world, in turn leading to high growth in consumer and retail markets, thus presenting massive investment and business opportunities. Food and grocery accounts for the majority share of the retail market in India followed by apparel and footwear, consumer durables and IT segments:

Category wise breakup of total retail market

Food &grocery	65.0%
Apparel & footwear	9.8%
Consumer durables & IT	9.2%
Jewellery& accessories	7.1%
Health & entertainment	3.7%
Home décor & furnishings	2.7%
Beauty & personal care	2.0%
Others	0.5%

Source: KONNECTED to consumers; Economist Intelligence Unit, accessed in April 2018

While traditional format dominates the retail market, share of organised segment is rapidly growing.

Source: KONNECTED to consumers; Economist Intelligence Unit, 2018

According to a report by Deloitte (2017), the high growth in e-commerce market is majorly attributable to factors including:

- **Growing internet penetration:** Internet users in India are expected to increase from 432 million in 2016 to 647 million by 2021, taking the internet penetration from 30 percent in 2016 to 59 percent in 2021. Approximately 75 percent of the new internet users are expected to come from rural regions.
- **Rising number of online shoppers:** The number of online shoppers would increase from the current 15 percent of the online population to 50 percent by 2026.
- **Increasing usage of smart phones:** Smartphone users in India are expected to increase from 260 million in 2016 to around 450 million by 2021, which is also likely to drive the e-commerce sales from USD 10.5 billion in 2016 to USD 38 billion in 2020.

Trends shaping the retail industry in India:

1. From affluence to influence:

In India the consumption story is highly promising, with the consumer base which is young, is becoming more urban, and has more purchasing power. Earlier consumers used to identify with the products they bought and the bragging rights that came with them. However, now they identify with products based on how- and how much- they can influence and impact the community around them, including their social circle. Consumer behaviours are shifting from being affluence-driven to being influence-led.

2. Increasing importance of millennial:

India has the world's largest millennial population in absolute terms. They fall in the age group of 18-35 years, and having a population of over 440 million, they constitute nearly 34 percent of the country's total population. Further, they account for a major share (nearly 48%) in the workforce population (Deloitte, October 2018). Millennial are the first global generation of digital communities, indicating that they are the first to witness and leverage technology and internet for shopping. Being better connected to information and being the chief wage earners in the household, millennial have significant spending power and greater access to products and services. This trend is expected to drive the consumer market in the country, leading to disruptions, especially in discretionary segments where the millennial group, in general, has a greater tendency to spend more vis-à-vis their increasing disposable incomes.

The key characteristics of the evolving customer needs of these millennial have been identified below:

- **Greater emphasis on health care and wellness**– Millennial are increasingly becoming health conscious and placing higher importance on physical and emotional wellbeing, and thus swiftly moving towards healthier and organic options. Research indicates that 36percent of the Indian millennial have a fitness app installed on their phones and about 45 percent think leading a healthy life is essential(The Economic Times, 2 November 2017). Therefore, even though 'eating out' as a concept has significantly increased, specifically amongstmillennial, focus on healthy alternatives is also on the rise. Even under the personal care category, there is a growing reliance on nature-based/ organic cures. Customers are looking for chemical free, ayurvedic products for their daily skincare regime, and hence, a large number of leading and upcoming brands are focusing on the same.
- **Importance of convenience**– Convenience is an important consideration for millennial on account of their hectic lifestyle. For the working younger generation, dearth of time is one of the key reasons for the growth in online shopping and online ordering from restaurants. It is for this reason that the 'ready to eat' product category has grown exponentially over the last five years.
- **Need for personalisation**– Millennialaim at differentiating themselves from the rest of the crowd and they prefer personalised product and service categories. They attach more importance to aesthetic aspects than to core functional aspect. Thus, personalisation is gaining focus.

3. Rise of multichannel retail:

In the current multichannel age, consumer companies in India are aligning their business strategies, especially to cater to the demands of a young and technologydriven population. Leading consumer companies are facing stiff competition in their omnichannel offerings, while aiming to provide seamless and integrated solutions to consumers' needs. The advent of technology has led to consumers leveraging multiple channels for making their purchases:

- Browsing online and shopping in-store for product's look and feel;
- Short listing products in-store and making the purchase online for better prices and offers;
- Getting custom/exclusive products shipped from foreign countries through company websites;
- Tele-ordering products for ease of access;
- Ordering products after reading reviews/recommendations on social media;
- Picking products from store/delivery centre after ordering online to avoid last-mile delivery delays (click and collect model);
- Placing personalised product orders instore to get them delivered later;
- Consumer-to-consumer (C2C) buying.

Internet and mobile apps have made the shopping journey of consumers convenient to the extent that the millennial and younger generations have now become habituated to instant gratification. Millennial are seen to be keen on socialising and collaboration, and thus, companies need to consider proactively streamlining their two-way communication with consumers. It is owing to this twoway communication that a new model of consumer-to-business (C2B) has emerged where companies get cues to new products and services through crowd sourcing. Consumers are conveying their specific needs to companies which are being used for creating brand value and providing unique experiences to consumers.

4. Consumer experience taking front seat:

The evolving consumer markets are seen to have shifted stance from 'bricks versus clicks' to 'bricks-and-clicks'. While earlier it was a battle between the online and offline channels, now the

industry seems to be moving towards a more immersive model in current times where collaboration is considered to be the key. The confluence of online and offline channels is expected to drive the markets, where consumer experience takes the limelight. The expectations from a modern brick-and-mortar store have transformed completely – consumers no longer walk-in to the stores just to buy the products. They are looking forward to an enhanced shopping experience where they get immersed into a whole new dimension and get to know about new products and features, engage with technology and devices, experience delectable global cuisines, get absorbed into virtual entertainment, special events and product launches, etc. Retail is thus evolving into a new dimension of ‘retailtainment’ or ‘retail and entertainment’, which is likely to dominate the consumer industry in the near future

New age consumers’ characteristics:

- **Changing purchase patterns:** With increasing internet penetration in India, online buyers are rapidly increasing. Moreover, m-Commerce is growing at an exponential pace, m-wallets transactions in India increased from INR 200 billion in FY16 to INR 3,000 billion in FY18 (Deloitte analysis).
- **Connected consumers:** Consumers in today’s world are more connected than ever. They are empowered by technology to get what they want, when they want and where they want.
- **Experiential shopping:** Consumers increasingly prefer to buy from modern retail stores with spacious layouts. While there are multiple options from where a product can be bought, shopping experience is becoming the key differentiator amongst channels.
- **Preference for convenience:** In today’s world of cash-rich and time-starved consumers, convenience has become a paramount consideration.
- **Healthy choices** Increasing sedentary lifestyle and changing eating habits has made way for healthier choices including natural, herbal, organic and Ayurvedic.

5. Technology stepping up the retail play:

Technology has been the front-runner in driving engagement and experience in consumers’ shopping journey. Apart from understanding consumers’ behavioural insights through advanced data analytics, emerging technologies such as IoT, AR and VR, Artificial Intelligence (AI), bots and drones, beacons, cloud-platforms, etc. have played a key role in enhancing consumers’ engagement more than ever.

- **Consumer alerts through beacons:** Beacons are small, battery-operated wireless devices that transmit coded messages to nearby paired smartphones using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). Since beacons deliver hyper contextualised content to users based on their location, they provide an extremely personalised experience to consumers and enhance their engagement with the brand. The technology is also leveraged majorly for proximity marketing and personalised recommendations, where consumers receive brand advertisements and suggestions if they pass through an nearby brand store.
- **Conversational commerce through voice-activated assistance:** Voice-activated assistance devices are witnessing a growing demand driven by the consumers’ increasing disposable income, rising social status consciousness, and greater preference for convenience. While the technology is at a nascent stage for ‘Conversational Commerce’, it is expected to be widely accepted by consumers around the world to complete their purchases. Currently, the tech-enabled devices are used majorly for playing music, setting alarms, searching for information, ordering cabs, etc.
- **RFID for tracking inventory:** Widely accepted and used across consumer businesses, RFID enables companies to keep a tab on their inventory positions by tagging products at

the time of manufacturing and allowing them to be tracked until the distribution process. Similarly, few companies also allow consumers to check specific products online, a process enabled through RFID.

- **Smart shopping carts and self-checkouts:** Major global consumer giants are testing varied versions of smart shopping carts, some of them being self-driven as well. With smart shopping carts, consumer companies intend to enhance the shopping experience of consumers and set new benchmarks of convenience. These carts are expected to serve as a direct response to online shopping, as they would guide consumers to the products in their shopping list and enable self-check-outs. Similarly, companies are also testing the concept of smart shelves, which consist of multiple sensors, each sensing a unique aspect of the product – weight, dimension, form, packaging intact or open, etc. These individual information pieces together combine to a broader product picture, which enables the sensors to track the product purchase and automatically update the shopper's bill, based on the product pickings. Coupled with deep machine learning algorithms, these information pieces can be stitched together to provide highly insightful shopping characteristics of consumers, which is expected to further open up multiple channels for companies to personalise their offerings for each set of consumers.
- **Touch less commerce through contactless payment methods:** With the advent of fintech, payment means have increased manifold. While traditionally, consumers used to make the payment for their purchases through cash or plastic money. However, the rise of internet and other payment methods including net-banking, online cash transfers, mobile wallets, single touch payments, payment through scanning code, etc. have shown an exponential increase in the country. Moreover, “selfie payments” is another advance and innovative payment solution, which is expected to revamp the payment process across consumer markets and other industries. Being already rolled out by a few finance and consumer companies across different parts of the world, the technology leverages “facial recognition” to authenticate payments. Further, to address the concern of security, as photographs could also be used to authenticate the payment process, companies require the consumer to make a particular gesture while looking at the camera – a blink, or a smile, or a wave, etc.
- **Automated product delivery at consumers' doorstep:** Major consumer brands across the globe are investing in innovative ways for making product delivery seamless, convenient, and cheaper. With brands exploring multiple ways of leveraging a host of channels to accomplish the last leg of consumers' shopping journey, new delivery models are increasingly coming up. Consumer experience and instant gratification seem to be the main drivers behind these innovations. Brands are experimenting with automated delivery through self-driven and AI-enabled trucks, which drive to consumers' pre-fed locations, deliver the products at consumers' doorstep and alert respective consumers on their Smartphone app. Similarly, pioneering brands in consumer markets and retail are also testing delivery by drones through aerial route. Innovations like these present a promising future to the delivery challenges, especially the last mile delivery concern in India.

6. Social commerce for 'We shopping':

Significance of 'S-commerce' or social commerce has significantly increased in today's world of connected consumers. Pictures and videos of products/brands posted by consumers on social networking sites and blogs, user experiences and stories shared on the web, ratings, reviews and recommendations posted online, etc. act as user-generated advertorial content. This content either promotes or demotes particular product, brand, or service amongst a specific set of people that have access to view/read the content. Since consumers can freely post information regarding their purchases or experiences on various social platforms and express their views, social media

has become a great tool for companies to engage with consumers. Companies are leveraging various analytical tools and advanced analytics are being used to analyse the social and behavioural traits of the consumers and tweak their strategies accordingly to suit the consumers' needs and convenience. Social sites are also used frequently to raise queries or post grievances which keep the consumer companies on toes to respond promptly to such concerns and avoid any damage to their social rapport.

Social media platforms and online product/ service reviews form an important part of the millennial' shopping journey as it influences their purchase decisions:

7. Personalisation:

Personalization continues to be a winning strategy to connect with the consumers, as brands are looking at opportunities to deliver a deeper level of precision in customization and tailored products and services. Innovations in data-driven, tailor-made offerings are giving consumers new inspiration and ways to “make it mine.” The results are so customized to the customers' needs that their satisfaction is nearly assured. Consumer brands across industry segments such as food and beverage, apparel and footwear, fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG), skin and personal care, etc. are increasingly focusing on differentiating from the competition by offering more than just the product. Retailers, both offline and online, are now looking to provide customised solutions to the consumers.

8. Premiumisation:

This trend started in India in the year 2016 and it is one of the major trends across consumer markets. There are many factors leading to the growth of this concept such as rising personal disposable income, changing lifestyle, and giving preference to convenience. Many retail sectors such as food and beverage, FMCG, apparel and footwear, consumer durables and electronics, etc. are using this concept. With the rapid growth of millennial as the major consumer segment, the perception of a product's value and premiumisation has also altered. Consumers no longer consider a product premium based on just a high price tag. Globally, less than one-third (31 percent) of the consumers consider a product premium only because it is expensive. Thus, a clear demand for value-for-money is emerging amongst the younger consumers.

9. Resonating core brand values:

The rapid use of technology in the consumer market space and the rising preference for convenience are seen to be constantly challenging the consumer brand loyalty. In the current fast-paced environment, attracting and retaining consumers to a particular brand requires significant time and effort investments. Further, consumers' shopping traits and preference nuances would need to be analysed in depth to offer customised products and services that match their requirements. Innovation in products and tailored service offerings such as personalized loyalty programs, convenient after sales services, etc. could assist in attracting consumers towards a particular brand. However, to have a sustainable, long-lasting relation with consumers, it may be necessary to have such brand values that resonate with the target consumer group's

core values. Imbibing such values would not only help companies build a strong brand image, but also lead to repeat consumers, implying more business.

10. Building a 'Future Fit' retail organisation:

The advent of digital in retail has provided opportunities for retailers to acquire new customers, engage better with existing customers, reduce the cost of operations, and improve employee motivation along with various other benefits that have a positive influence from a revenue and margin perspective. Digital has impacted three key elements of the retail business and operating model:

- **Strategy** – Disruptions such as Internet of Things, Big Data Analytics, Artificial Intelligence, Predictive Analytics, Automation, Dark Analytics, Virtual and Augmented Reality and Blockchain have led to the onset of some fundamental changes in retail strategy and business models.
- **Front end** – The impact of digital on the front end of the retail value chain is significant and revolves around “the digital customer” experience as the pivot, with merchandising, promotions, loyalty programmes as well as point of sale (PoS) related digital solutions enriching that experience.
- **Back end** – Digital is driving the retail organisations to become more agile. It is impacting various facets of the back end in following manner:

Supply chain– Shift from traditional supply chain (information travels linearly, in a sequential chain of events) to digital supply chain (each supply node becomes more capable and connected, resulting in an integrated network)

Logistics and warehousing– The rise of e-commerce has led to new digital entrants in the last-mile delivery market. Digital platforms are expected to become increasingly important in the logistics industry, allowing small companies in India to have a global reach and compete with the sector's established giants. Information services, shared logistics capabilities, delivery capabilities, etc. are the key digital themes of logistics to get affected by digital.

Finance– Today, digital finance is far beyond incremental technology tweaks. It is an ecosystem that brings together the forces of exponential computing power and the behavioural disruptions of socio-economic forces. Digital finance is the next generation finance ecosystem that utilises disruptive technology, innovation, data, and people to elevate and differentiate the capabilities of the finance function.

Procurement and vendor management– Low-cost computing and data storage have enabled advancements in mobile technology and the cloud. Constant connectivity is the norm, and sensors bring devices and machines to life in the Internet of Things. The application of these disruptive technologies to procurement is already fundamentally altering the impact of this function. Strategic sourcing is becoming more predictive, transactional procurement is getting more automated, and supplier relationship management is becoming more proactive.

Assortment mix and planning– While traditional retail assortment-mix and planning focuses on the product, today's most successful brands focus on the customer when making retail assortment planning decisions. To attract shopper traffic, companies now adopt a demand-driven, customer-centric assortment optimisation strategy. This is enabled by digital transformation, which in turn brings accuracy to the assortment mix and planning process.

People– The definition of success, which was extensively around attracting and retaining customers and providing consistent customer experience earlier, has now expanded to encompass the employee aspect as well.

Conclusion:

India is at the cusp of evolution in the consumer markets. It has a major share of relatively young population, and thus retailers need to learn from millennials for strategy and innovation to offer

products/ services catering to their needs and consequently expand the offerings from niche to masses. In the current era of connected consumers and multi-channel retail, instant gratification has become a key priority. Retailers must engage with consumers to enhance brand connect and provide them with a memorable shopping experience. To facilitate this engagement, brands have to accelerate digital investments to cater to the new-age shoppers. As consumers and businesses become more connected, investing in technology for data and cyber security gains significant importance. Further, with the opening up of consumer markets for FDIs, various foreign brands have entered Indian markets to reap the benefits of an ever-growing consumer opportunity. Retailers need to deliver value and convenience to be competitive in this cut-throat environment. Given the strong retail and consumer outlook, India is expected to witness redefining trends in the consumer markets, which will shape the future of the retail industry in India. Consumer experience will be the key focus of the companies and technology will facilitate the enhancement of consumers' experience throughout their shopping journey. Consumer behaviours are undergoing a fundamental shift from being affluence driven to being influence led. Today's consumers are experience-seeking, hyper connected, socially influenced, value-driven, and hungry for personalisation. This shift will force retailers to move beyond product, pricing, and convenience to focus on the customer experience. The retailers who can deliver a superior experience will build a sustainable competitive advantage, drive profitable growth, and emerge as winners.

References:

1. Dhruv Grewal, Scott Motyka, and Michael Levy. (2018). The Evolution and Future of Retailing and Retailing Education. *Journal of Marketing Education* 2018, Vol. 40(1) 85–93.
2. Grewal, D., Roggeveen, A., & Nordfält, J. (2017). The future of retailing. *Journal of Retailing*, 93(1), 1-6.
3. Rafaeli, A., Altman, D., Gremler, D. D., Huang, M.-H., Grewal, D., Iyer, B., . . . Ruyter, K. d. (2017). The future of frontline research: A glimpse through the eyes of thought leaders. *Journal of Service Research*, 30(1), 91-99.
4. Roggeveen, A. L., Grewal, D., Townsend, C., & Krishnan, R. (2015, November). The impact of dynamic presentation format on consumer preferences for hedonic products and services. *Journal of Marketing*, 79, 34-49.
5. Roggeveen, A. L., Nordfält, J., & Grewal, D. (2016). Do digital displays enhance sales? Role of retail format and message content. *Journal of Retailing*, 92, 122-131.
6. The Economic Times, 2 November 2017. What the millennial Indian wants: Not cars & houses, just fun & convenience.
7. A T Kearney (2019), "Indian Retail: It's time to create stores with stories", available at www.atkearney.in
8. Deloitte (2017), "KONNECTED to consumers", available at www2.deloitte.com
9. Deloitte (2018), "Consumer LEADS", available at www2.deloitte.com
10. Deloitte (2019), "Unravelling the Indian Consumer", available at www2.deloitte.com